

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCE BETWEEN US DMF, CANADIAN DMF AND EDMF

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The submission of a DMF is not required by law or FDA regulation, it is submitted solely at the discretion of the DMF holder. The DMF contains factual and complete information on a drug product's chemistry, manufacture, stability, purity, impurity profile, packaging, and the cGMP status of any human drug product. The present work gives the Detailed idea on how to file Drug Master File in US, EUROPE, CANADA, AUSTRALIA. **Approach:** A Drug Master File is a submission of information to the FDA to permit the FDA to review this information in support of a third party's submission without revealing the information to the third party. In US, DMF filing was done through NDA for drugs, ANDA for generics and BLA for Biologics. In Europe, DMF filing was done through MAA via centralized procedure for eligible

products and for other products via decentralized procedure was used. In CANADA, DMF filing was done through NDS for both drugs and biologic products, where as in AUSTRALIA different application processes and regulatory requirements apply depending on the type of therapeutic goods that is applied. **Findings:** This gives you clear vision on how to file Drug master file in US, EUROPE, CANADA and AUSTRALIA. This paper also gives you the comparison of DMF fling procedure in the above-mentioned countries so that reader can have clear idea on how to file DMF and different concerns on DMF among the above counties. **Conclusion:** The DMF contains factual and complete information on a drug product's chemistry, manufacture, stability, purity, impurity profile, Packaging and the cGMP status of any Drug product for humans. The content and the format for Drug Master File is used to obtain marketing Authorization. The main objective of the DMF is to support regulatory requirements

of a medicinal product to prove its quality, safety and efficacy. This helps to obtain a marketing authorization grant. Now from 2016 onwards most of the regulated countries will use eCTD or their electronic format for their DMF submission.

KEYWORDS: DMF, FDA, CDR, CMC, CEP, LOA, TGA, ACPM, ACSOM, NDS, MAA, ANDA A Drug Master File (DMF) is a submission to the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) that may be used to provide confidential detailed information about facilities, processes, or articles used in the manufacturing, processing, packaging, and storing of one or more human drugs.

INTRODUCTION

Drug Master File (DMF) is a submission to the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) that may be used to provide confidential, detailed information about facilities, processes, or articles used in the manufacturing, processing, 1 packaging, and storing of one or more human drugs.

DMFs usually cover the Chemistry, Manufacturing and Controls (CMC) of a component of a drug product e.g. drug substance, Excipients, packaging material. Drug product information or non-CMC information may be filed in a DMF.

A DMF is required to supply bulk Drugs to the United States but the FDA does not require all manufacturers to submit a DMF. However, the information contained in a DMF may be used to support an Investigational New Drug Application (IND), a New Drug Application (NDA), an Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA), another DMF, an Export Application, or related documents.

Before going to the details of DMF submission in different countries, an understanding between differences prevailing in Application procedures and DMF are given below:

POINTS TO BE NOTED IN THE PROCESS OF DMF SUBMISSION

DMF Does not come under regulatory status as it is not mandatory to file it.

• DMFs are entered into database as per their types. (Separate database for each type of DMF).

• Submitted to Central Drug Registration (CDR).

• No assignment to a reviewer, no due date.

• DMFs are reviewed only when referred by an application or DMF.

• If the anniversary date for annual update is missed FDA will not send a reminder.

Types of DMF Submission

Therapeutic goods can be very beneficial, but to be effective they must be modified the way they work on body systems. This means there are risks, as well as benefits, associated with their use. Because of these risks, these products must be regulated in order to protect public health.

The following information gives you an idea of Drug submission types in US, Europe, Canada and Australia.

USA

1. New Drug Application (NDA), for new drugs.
2. Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA)-for generics.
3. Biologic License Application (BLA), for biologics.

EUROPE

1. Marketing Authorization Application (MAA) via the centralized procedure for eligible products.
2. For other products, via the decentralized, mutual recognition or national authorization are applicable.

CANADA

New Drug Submission (NDS) for both drugs and biologic products.

AUSTRALIA

1. Different application processes and regulatory requirements apply depending on the type of therapeutic good that is to be supplied.
2. The Australian Regulatory Guidelines for Prescription Medicines (ARGPM) will assist sponsors to prepare applications to register new prescription or other high-risk medicines for human use in Australia.
3. The Australian Regulatory Guidelines for OTC Medicines (ARGOM) will assist sponsors to prepare applications for a new OTC medicine for human use in Australia.
4. The Australian Regulatory Guidelines for Complementary Medicines (ARGCM) will assist sponsors to prepare applications for new complementary medicine for human use in Australia.
5. The Australian Regulatory Guidelines for Medical Devices (ARGMD) will assist

manufacturers and sponsors of medical devices in meeting the regulatory requirements for legally supplying a medical device in Australia.

6. The Australian Regulatory Guidelines for Biological (ARGB) will assist sponsors to prepare applications to register a new biological for human use in Australia.
7. Another therapeutic good (OTG) includes things such as disinfectants and tampons.

DMF types

Master Files (DMFs) are required in most countries as supporting documents for the registration of drug products. DMFs generally contain information pertaining to the chemistry, manufacturing and controls (CMC) sections of the drug submission and reflect the drug's identity, strength, purity and quality.

The DMF procedure exists all over the world, from highly regulated markets (HRMs) through nearly regulated markets (NRMs). The HRMs, such as the US, EU, Japan, Canada and Australia, exclusively use DMF procedures, whereas NRMs, including Brazil, Russia and South Africa, utilize a system called a technical package. In less regulated markets (LRMs), no DMF procedure exists. For example, India, which is classified as an LRM, has neither a DMF system nor a technical package.

All these issues are covered by guidelines, published by the various international regulatory authorities such as the US Food and Drug Administration, European Medicines Agency, Australian Therapeutic Goods Administration, Canadian Health Protection and Foods Branch and several others.

US DMF – TYPES

Type I- Manufacturing Site, Facilities, Operating Procedures, and Personnel. This is no longer accepted by the FDA.

Type II – Drug Substance, Drug Substance Intermediate, and Material Used in Their Preparation, or Drug Product

Type III – Packaging

Type IV – Excipients, Colorant, Flavour, Essence, or Material Used in Their Preparation

Type V – FDA Accepted Reference Information Used for sterile manufacturing plants and contract facilities 3 for biotech products.

US DMF Filing System Filing the DMF

1. Holder sends two copies of the DMF to FDA
2. DMF is reviewed for administrative purposes only by Central Document Room staff.
3. DMF entered into database, assigned a number and acknowledgment letter sent to holder
4. A DMF is neither approved or disapproved

Accessing the DMF: Letter of Authorization (LOA)

1. The DMF will be reviewed only when it is referenced in an application or another
2. The Holder must submit two copies of the LOA to the DMF, plus a copy to the Applicant.
3. The Applicant submits a copy of the LOA in their Application.
4. The LOA is the only mechanism to trigger a review of the DMF by the FDA.

DMF Review Procedure

1. The DMF is reviewed only if referenced by an Applicant or another DMF
2. If the reviewer finds deficiencies in the DMF, the deficiencies are detailed in a letter to the Holder.
3. The Applicant will be notified that deficiencies exist, but the nature of the deficiencies is not communicated to the Applicant.

Format, Font, Font Size and Paper used for submission to USFDA

1. Electronic DMF should be filed. In Common Technical Document, the display of information should be unambiguous and transparent, in order to facilitate the review of the basic data and to help a reviewer become quickly oriented to the application contents.
2. Text and tables should be prepared using margins that allow the document to be printed on both A4 paper (E.U. and Japan) and 8.5 x11" paper (U.S.). The left-hand margin should be sufficiently large that information is not obscured by the method of binding. Font sizes for text and tables should be of a style and size that are large enough to be easily legible, even after photocopying.
3. Times New Roman, 12-point font is recommended for narrative text. Every page should be numbered, according to the granularity document. Acronyms and abbreviations should be defined the first time they are used in each module.
4. DMF neither approved nor disapproved by USFDA.
5. U.S. standard paper size (8.5 by 11 inches) is preferred.

6. Paper length should not be less than 10 inches nor more than 12 inches. However, it may occasionally be necessary to use individual pages larger than standard paper size to present a floor plan, synthesis diagram, batch formula, or manufacturing instructions. Those pages should be folded and mounted to allow the page to be opened for review without disassembling the jacket and refolded without damage when the volume is shelved.
7. The agency's system for filing DMF's provides for assembly on the left side of the page. The left margin should be at least three fourths of an inch to assure that text is not obscured in the fastened area. The right margin should be at least one half of an inch. The submitter should punch holes 8 1/2 inches apart in each page.

Referral letters required for FDA submission

In CTD (Common Technical Document), in Module 1 – Administrative Information provide information about referral letters for FDA submission.

Letter of Authorization (LOA)

Submission by the owner of information, giving authorization for the information to be used by another. An Agent Appointment Letter is NOT an LOA 5 and should not be called "Letter of Authorization"

Statement of Right of Reference

Submission by recipient of a Letter of Authorization with a copy of the LOA and statement of right of reference. Submitted in a DMF only when another DMF is referenced. If a DMF holder references other DMFs a list of those DMFs can be provided in this section. This is not the same as the list of authorized parties.

List of authorized persons to incorporate by reference

This list should be submitted in DMF annual reports.

EUROPEAN DMF – TYPES

European DMF was established in 1989-1991. It was revised in 2005 and became ASMF (Active Substance Master File) after implementation of Common Technical Document (CTD) in EU. DMF is applicable only to active substances.

The content and the format for DMF used in United States differ from that used in European Countries to obtain market authorization (MA). The Main Objective of the EDMF is to support

regulatory requirements of a medicinal product to prove its quality, safety and efficacy. This helps to obtain a Marketing Authorisation grant.

European DMF has been divided into 2 parts

1. Applicant Part (Open): Contains all the required information including an outline of the manufacturing method.
2. ASM Restricted Part (Closed / Confidential): Confidential information of on the manufacturing 5 of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient.

European DMF Filing System

The applicant's part of a DMF is provided by the ASM (Active Substance Manufacturer) to the applicant directly and becomes part of the application for marketing authorization. Both the applicant's part and the ASM Restricted Part of the DMF are submitted to the authorities.

The main objective of the Active Substance Master File (ASMF) procedure, formerly known as the European Drug Master File (EDMF) procedure, is to allow valuable confidential intellectual property or 'knowhow' of the manufacturer of the active substance (ASM) to be protected, while at the same time allowing the Applicant or Marketing Authorisation (MA) holder to take full responsibility for the medicinal product and the quality and quality control of the active substance. National Competent Authorities/EMA thus have access to the complete information that is necessary for an evaluation of the suitability of the use of the active substance in the 6 medicinal products.

The ASMF procedure can be used for the following active substances, including herbal active substances/preparations. i.e.:

New active substances

Existing active substances: not included in the European Pharmacopoeia (Ph. Eur.) or the pharmacopoeia of an EU Member State.

Pharmacopoeia active substances included in the Ph. Eur. or in the pharmacopoeia of an EU Member State.

Applicant's part of a DMF – Open part

The applicant must be supplied by the ASM with sufficient information to be able to take responsibility for an evaluation of the suitability of the active substance specification to control the quality of the substance. This normally includes a brief outline of the manufacturing

method, information on potential impurities originating from the manufacturing method, from the isolation procedure (natural products) or from degradation and, where applicable, information on the toxicity of specific impurities.

ASM Restricted Part of DMF – Closed part

Detailed information on the individual steps of the manufacturing method such as reaction conditions, temperature, validation and evaluation data for certain critical steps of the manufacturing method, etc. and on quality control during manufacture may contain valuable know-how. Such information may therefore be supplied to the authorities only.

CANADA DMF – TYPES

Canada has 4 Types of DMFs

Type I (Active Substance Master Files (ASMF))

For pharmaceuticals

Drug substance or intermediate in the manufacture of a drug substance. This can include Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (API).

For biologics

Drug substance can include bulk process intermediates, vaccine antigens, Excipients of biological origin (with the exception of gelatine) - Drug Substance, Drug Intermediates and materials used in their preparations.

Type II - Container Closure System Master Files (CCS MFs) Type III - Excipients Master Files (EMFs)

Excipients, capsule shells, coating ingredients, colorants, flavours, and other additives, including alum and growth media.

Type IV - Dosage form Master Files (DFMFs) Dosage forms and drug product intermediates Canadian DMF Filing System

Filing the DMF

Type I ASMFs and Type IV Dosage Form Master Files are divided in two parts:

The "Restricted Part" and the "Applicant's Part" which is provided to the Applicant and is usually included as part of the applicant's drug submission or clinical trial application (CTA),

with the accompanying Letter of Access (LoA).

For Type I ASMFs, the Applicant's Part contains the information that the ASMF Holder regards as nonconfidential to the applicant, whereas the Restricted Part contains the information that the ASMF Holder regards as confidential. An MF will not be considered complete if both parts have not been provided to Health Canada.

Registration requirements

For New MF Registrations, the following electronic documents are required:

1. One signed cover letter, including the MF name
2. MF Agent Authorization Letter from MF Holder, if applicable
3. MF Application Form
4. Master File Fee Form and appropriate fees
5. Certificate of Suitability (CEP) and Attestations (for Type I MFs only), if applicable
6. Letter(s) of Access
7. For Type I ASMFs and Type IV Dosage Form Master Files, the following additional electronic documents are required:
 8. The MF must include the Applicant and the Restricted Parts
 9. A Copy of Quality Overall Summary (QOS) in Word format
 10. The Certified Product Information Document (CPID) in Word format, if applicable.

For Type II CCS MFs and Type III Excipient MFs, multiple components may be included in a single MF provided that the components are similar (e.g., a complete container closure system, different stopper formulations, multiple flavours). A limit of 50 components will be enforced per MF. Additional components should be filed in a new MF.

NAMING AN MF

For Type I ASMFs, the preferred name of the MF should be the generic name (e.g., the International Non-proprietary Name (INN) for an active pharmaceutical ingredient) followed by any manufacturer's internal API brand names or codes to identify a particular product.

A Type IV Dosage Form Master File may have more than one product strength with the same formulation except for changes necessary to accommodate the different strengths. However, in such cases, the information in the MFs for each product should be clearly differentiated within the Dosage Form Master Files.

If the MF Holder has more than one MF for a similar product, the cover letter should state this explicitly and provide information to distinguish the different products. The MF Holder should provide an MF name that distinguishes the MF from any previously registered MFs.

Accessing the DMF: Letter of Authorization (LOA)

MF Holders file confidential business information (CBI) directly with Health Canada that may be referenced to support an applicant's drug submission or CTA with respect to Quality information. The information in the MF will only be used if the MF Holder provides Health Canada with a signed original LoA to the MF Applicant. The LoA grants Health Canada permission to access the information contained in the MF.

Information To Include in the LoA

The following information should be included in the LoA:

1. MF number, if assigned by Health Canada, if not yet assigned state "to be assigned"
2. Name of MF
3. Manufacturer's Internal Code, if applicable
4. Applicant's Name being granted access to the MF
5. The appropriate Master File Fee Form and Fees

LoA Filing

A separate LoA is required for each applicant who cross-references the MF in their drug submission or CTA and each letter is subject to the applicable fees. A LoA needs to be signed by the MF Holder. A copy of the LoA should be sent to the applicant prior to filing their drug submission or CTA.

For Type I and IV, a LoA is for an MF in its entirety and is valid for all products from the applicant cross referencing the MF. For Type II or III, a LoA can be filed to grant access for an entire MF or specific components within a MF. Only one LoA is required, per applicant, if granting access to the entire MF or for multiple components within a MF. When granting access for an additional component, not included in the first LoA, a new LoA is required with the applicable fee.

When a MF Holder is filing a Type IV Dosage Form Master File that references a Type I ASMF, the MF Holder for the Type I ASMF must file a LoA granting access to the MF Holder of the Type IV Dosage Form Master File. Separate LoA's must be filed granting the applicant

access to the Type I ASMF and to the Type IV 8 Dosage Form Master File as well.

PROCESSING OF DMF

MFs are processed in sequence according to the date of receipt. When a MF registration package is received the following activities are performed:

1. Assigning an MF number and a dossier ID to the MF (only for New MF registration submissions)
2. Verifying that the correct information, documents and forms have been filed and that all submitted information, documents and forms are complete for administrative purposes (including those related to cost-recovery).

Once the MF registration package is administratively complete:

1. A filing date is assigned (which is the date when the MF is considered administratively complete),
2. An acknowledgement letter is sent to the designated MF contact as listed on the MF.

APPLICATION FORM

If required information, forms or fees are missing or incomplete, the MF will be placed on Administrative Hold, in which case the Office of Submissions and Intellectual Property (OSIP) will issue an MF transaction rejection letter to the MF contact requesting the missing information.^[8]

ADMINISTRATIVE HOLDS

At different stages during the administrative processing of MFs it may be necessary to place the MF transaction on Administrative Hold when the MF package is incomplete (i.e. missing required information and material). This hold will remain in place until the required information is submitted.

There are two categories of administrative holds:

A. Process Hold

OSIP will place the MF on Process Hold when the MF is considered incomplete, or when the information is filed as the wrong transaction type (i.e., New MF should have been filed as an Update). When the reason for the Process Hold is addressed, the MF transaction is considered administratively complete and a filing date will be applied.

B. Cost Recovery Hold

In the event that the Master File Fee Form or applicable fee is not provided or the applicable fee is insufficient, OSIP will request the fee form and payment from the MF contact. Pending receipt of the fee form or payment, the transaction will be placed on a Cost Recovery Hold. If the fee form or payment is not received in the timeframe indicated in the letter issued by cost recovery, the transaction will not be accepted. When the reason for the Cost Recovery Hold is addressed, the submission is considered administratively complete and a filing date will be applied.

Failure to respond to a request for additional or corrected information in the prescribed time will result in the MF being shredded and/or closed.

Format and Structure of the MF

MFs must follow the filing and formatting requirements outlined in the Guidance Document Preparation of Drug Regulatory Activities in the "None CTD Electronic-Only" Format which includes guidance on MF structure and content as well as the breakdown of the Applicant and the Restricted Parts.

All documents should be provided in Portable Document Format (PDF) or Microsoft Word. Documents may also be provided in Microsoft Excel where applicable.

Official Language of Correspondence

The MF can be filed in either of Canada's official languages (English or French) (8).

AUSTRALIA DMF

AUSTRALIA DMF – TYPES

Category 1

Category 2

Category 1 and 2 applications for new registrations are made under section 23 of the Act. Section 23 requires that applications are made in a form approved by the Secretary. The currently approved form is the CTD format.

AUSTRALIA DMF Filing System

An Australian DMF registration system consists of the following stages.

• Phase 1: Pre Submission

• Phase 2: Submission

ÿ Phase 3: First Round of Assessment

ÿ Phase 4: Consolidated section 31 request response

ÿ Phase 5: Second round assessment ÿ Phase 6: Expert Advisory Review ÿ Phase 7: Decision

ÿ Phase 8: Post Decision

Phase 1: Pre Submission

1. The pre-submission phase applies to category 1 and category 2 applications, excluding requests for additional trade names.
2. The pre-submission phase begins with the lodgement of the Pre-submission planning form (PPF). The PPF provides the TGA with the necessary information on the scope and scale of an application to arrange appropriate resourcing for the processing and evaluation of the application. Once a PPF has been considered complete and acceptable, the TGA begins the process of securing appropriate evaluators for the dossier.
3. A complete PPF identifies the proposed application type, and contains general information about the quality, nonclinical, and clinical evidence to be included in the dossier. The information provided in the PPF allows the TGA to commit to timeframes for the evaluation of the 9 applications.

Milestone 1

If the PPF is considered complete and acceptable, a TGA Planning letters sent to the applicant identifying the expected dossier lodgement date and target milestone dates for the application.

Phase 2: Submission

The submission phase involves processing activities in preparation for application evaluation.

1. Confirmation of dossier delivery by the expected lodgement date
2. Verification that any application fee has been paid
3. Workflow planning and IT administration
4. Consideration of the application against the TGA regulatory requirements
5. Issuing of a Notification letter, including notice of evaluation fee payable, if applicable.

Milestone 2

The TGA sends a letter to the applicant identifying whether the application has been considered effective and accepted for evaluation, or considered 'not effective'.

Phase 3: First Round of Assessment

1. All data provided in the dossier are considered by the evaluators during the first-round assessment phase.
2. Where there are issues or questions about any component of the application, a consolidated section 31 requests for information containing requests from all evaluation areas within the TGA is compiled and sent to the applicant by the date specified in the Planning letter.
3. Within this phase, TGA evaluators may directly contact the applicant to seek clarification or ask questions informally if they determine that waiting for the formal consolidated section 31 request on a minor clarification is unnecessary. This type of informal question will not change the timeline for the consolidated section 31 request.

Milestone 3

Applicants will be sent a Milestone 3 letter including:

• A consolidated section 31 request for information or documents, if required

• Copies of the first-round assessment reports prepared by the quality, nonclinical, clinical and RMP evaluators.

Phase 4: Consolidated section 31 request response

• the consolidated section 31 request response phase allows applicants time to consider the TGA's consolidated section 31 request for information or documents, prepare a response and send the response to the TGA.

Milestone 4

Applicants will send TGA a response to:

• Any consolidated section 31 request for Information or documents

• the first-round assessment reports prepared by the quality, nonclinical and clinical evaluators, if required.

Response to section 31 request

Responses to a section 31 request for information or documents must be provided in CTD format. Applicants need to send both hard copy and electronic copy formats of the response to the TGA.

Applicants should pay close attention to the questions raised in the s31 letter, as well as any

requests in the letter for other information or documents, as this may be the sole opportunity that an applicant has to provide this information.

Response to first round assessment reports

Applicants should review the first-round assessment reports and advise the TGA of any perceived errors of fact or major omissions. Each identified error of fact or omission must be referenced to information previously submitted.

Phase 5: Second round assessment

During the second-round assessment phase, evaluators will consider the response provided by the applicant to the section 31 request (if applicable) and complete the evaluation of the data.

Milestone 5

• All second-round assessment reports are 9 completed

Opportunity to review evaluation reports

Applicants will be given a period of 14 calendar days after the TGA issues the final evaluation report(s) in which to review and advise the TGA of any perceived errors of fact or major omissions outside the pre-ACPM response.

Applicants should also use this period to revise the draft PI based on recommendations in the evaluation reports.

Phase 6: Expert Advisory Review

After completion of the second-round assessment phase, the evaluation reports are considered by the delegate. The delegate may seek independent advice on issues concerning the application.

The main advisory group for prescription medicines is the Advisory Committee on Prescription Medicines (ACPM). Specific issues may also be referred to the Pharmaceutical Subcommittee (PSC) of the ACPM, or to the Advisory Committee on the Safety of Medicines (ACSOM).

Comments from the applicant in relation to perceived errors of fact or major omissions in the second-round assessment reports for those applications referred to the ACPM are also considered.

Milestone 6

The TGA notifies the applicant of the advice received from the ACPM.

Phase 7: Decision

The TGA delegate will determine whether the application is to be approved (possibly modified or varied) or rejected. Where any outstanding issues may affect the decision, the delegate may liaise directly with the applicant during this phase before finalising the decision.

For applications made under section 23 of the Act the applicant will be notified in writing of the decision within 28 days of it being made (Section 25(4) of the Act). The issuing of a decision ends the 10 legislated evaluation period.

Milestone 7

ÿ A decision is made for approval or rejection of the application for a new registration or for a variation to a registration and the decision letter is sent to 11 the applicant.

Phase 8: Post Decision

ÿ During the post-decision phase, administrative and regulatory activities are completed.

Milestone 8

ÿ Administrative and regulatory activities are completed. Any outstanding ÿ Payments are finalised (if applicable) and the ARTG entry is finalised.

The pharmaceutical industry is one of the most regulated industries; no drug would be marketed without the teams of medical researchers and other specialists who worked to make sure it receives regulatory authority's approval. Regulatory affairs professionals are key players in drug development for obtaining approvals and maintaining lifecycle management of both branded and generic drugs.^[1] They are the primary communications link between the company and agencies such as USFDA, MHRA, CDSCO and TPD etc. A regulatory authority is an agency of the government that is responsible for protecting public health in safety aspects. The present study focuses on API filing (DMF System) in United States, Canada and Europe.^[2] Drug Master File or DMF is a document prepared by a pharmaceutical manufacturer and submitted solely at its discretion to the appropriate regulatory authority in the intended drug market. There is no regulatory requirement to file a DMF. However, the document provides the regulatory authority with confidential, detailed information about facilities, processes, particles used in the manufacturing, processing, packaging, and storing

of one or more human drugs.^[3]

Typically, a DMF is filed when two or more firms work in partnership on developing or manufacturing a drug product. The DMF filing allows a firm to protect its intellectual property from its partner while complying with regulatory requirements for disclosure of processing details.

DMF GUIDELINES HISTORY IN USA, EUROPE AND CANADA^[4]

Guidelines in USA: In USA DMF guidelines are established in September 1989 Guideline for Drug Master Files. Guidance for Industry: Generic Drug User Fee Amendments of 2012 Guidelines in EUROPE: 31 May 2013- This guideline replaces guideline CPMP/QWP/227/0 Committee of Human Medicinal Products CHMP/QWP/227/02 Rev3/Corr * Committee of Veterinary Medicinal Products EMEA/CVMP/134/02 Rev3/Corr Discussion at the HMPC November 2005 – January 2006 Adoption by the HMPC – 22 January 2006 Draft agreed by Quality Working Party – 9 February 2006

Adoption by CHMP for release for consultation – 23 March 2006 Adoption by CVMP for release for consultation 20 April 2006 End of consultation (dead line for comments) – 30 August 2006 Agreed by Quality Working Party – 1 December 2011.

Adoption by CHMP for release for consultation – 15 December 2011 Adoption by CVMP for release for consultation – 12 January 2012 End of consultation (deadline for comments) – 12 March 2012.

Rev. 03 Agreed by Quality Working Party – 04 May 2012 Rev. 03 Adoption by CVMP – 14 June 2012

Rev. 03 Adoption by CHMP – 21 June 2012

Rev. 03 Date for coming into effect – 1 October 2012

Guidelines in CANADA: September 05, 2008

The draft version of this Health Canada guidance document Drug Master Files (DMF) is now available for comment. This guidance document is a revised version of the guidance document Product Master Files published in 1994 which will replace the 1994 document when it is officially adopted.

European DMF/ASMF5

EC procedure where information can be provided to the authorities and the applicant, where the active substance manufacturer is not the applicant for a product marketing authorization, with a view to protecting valuable manufacturing know-how. Established in 1989- 1991 Revised in 2005 and became ASMF (Active Substance Master File) after implementation of CTD in EU Applicable only to active substances has been divided into 2 parts-An applicant's part and an ASM Restricted Part. The applicant's part of a DMF is provided by the ASM (Active Substance Manufacturer) to the applicant directly and becomes part of the application for marketing authorization. Both the applicant's part and the ASM Restricted Part of the DMF are submitted to the authorities.

Canadian DMF's^[6]

A Drug Master File (DMF) is a reference that provides information about specific processes or components used in the manufacturing, processing, and packaging of a drug. The DMF is a useful vehicle for providing information to Health Canada, where that information is of a proprietary nature and is not available to the manufacturer of the dosage form or to a Sponsor of a submission when they are not the dosage form manufacturer. The DMF can be referenced by drug manufacturers in support of their New Drug Submissions (NDSs), Abbreviated New Drug Submissions (ANDSs), Supplement to a New Drug Submission (SNDS) Supplement to an Abbreviated New Drug Submission (SANDS), DIN submissions, Notifiable Changes (NCs), New Product Number (NPN) applications and Clinical Trial Applications (CTAs). DMFs may be referenced by more than one drug manufacturer. Canadian DMF: division of information to Sponsor's (Open) and Restricted (Closed) part for DMFs type I and IV.

CANADIAN DMFS

Type I- Drug substance or intermediate in the manufacture of DS Type II- Container-closure systems or components

Type III- Excipients, colorants, Flavors and other additives

Type IV- Dosage forms and drug product intermediates (e.g. blend of drug substance and excipients)

FEES FOR DMF FILLING^[7]

Under GDUFA, the DMF fee is owed by each person that owns a type II active pharmaceutical ingredient DMF that is referenced, on or after October 1, 2012, in a generic drug submission by an initial letter of authorization. This is a one-time fee for each individual DMF.

This fee is due no later than the date on which the first generic drug submission is submitted that references the associated DMF. Under section 744 B (a) (2)(D)(iii) of the FD&C Act, if a DMF has successfully undergone an initial completeness assessment and the fee is paid, the DMF will be placed on a publicly available list documenting DMFs available for reference. Thus, some DMF holders may choose to pay the fee prior to the date that it would otherwise be due in order to have the DMF placed on that list. In order to calculate the DMF fee, FDA assessed the volume of DMF submissions overtime.

The statistical forecasting methodology of power regression analysis was selected because these models how very good fit to the distribution of DMF submissions overtime. Based on the 8 months of available data representing the total paid DMFs from FY2013 and projecting a5-year timeline (October 2013 to October 2017), FDA is estimating 583 fee-paying DMFs for FY 2014. The FY 2014 DMF fee is determined by dividing the DMF revenue by the estimated number of fee-paying DMFs in FY 2014. Section744B (b) (2) (A) specifies that the DMF fees will make up 6 percent of the \$305,659,000, which is \$18,340,000 (rounded to the nearest thousand dollars). Dividing the DMF revenue amount (\$18,340,000) by the estimated fee-paying DMFs (583), and rounding to the nearest \$10, yields a DMF fee of \$31,460 for FY 2014.

Table 1: DMF Fees For Registration of Active Substance Manufacturers & Importer/Distributor.

Fees for Registration of Active Substance Manufactures		Fee	Notes
New Application	New application for registration as a manufacture of Active Substances	£5006	£3143 application fee plus £1863 assessment fee £2655 Inspection fee less £1863 assessment fee
	Additional fee if the risk assessment of the initial application triggers an inspection	£792	
	Inspection fee (per site if required)	£2655	Charged for inspections conducted post registration
Variations	Notification of changes (Variation)	£257	
	Inspection fee (per site if required)	£2655	

LITRATURE REVIEW

Chakraborty Krishnasis et al., (2020) DMF widely known as Drug Master File, is a kind of confidential document which covers all comprehensive, accurate and precise information about Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) or Finished Product Dosage Form (FP). The Drug master file consist of two parts, one the applicant's part which covers all the information that the license holder needs to review about quality of drug product & other one is the restricted

part which covers all the confidential information about the manufacturing process that can only be presented in front of health authorities. A DMF can be used by holder who establishes the file or by one or more parties in support of their files or applications. The present study is to brief an overview of DMF filing in different countries which are USA, Europe and Canada. In USA, Canada the drug master file is known as DMF and in EUROPE, known as ASMF (Active Substance Master File).^[20]

Kanti S P Yamini et al., (2019) DMF (Drug master file) is a kind of confidential document which contains complete, factual and correct information about active pharmaceutical ingredient or finished drug dosage form. A DMF can be used by holder who establishes the file or by one or more parties in support of their files or applications. The Drug master file consist of 2 parts: -(a) the applicant's part-that contains all the information that the license holder needs to review about quality of drug product & (b) the restricted part-which contains all the confidential information about the manufacturing process that can only be presented in front of authorities. The purpose of this article is to present an overview of DMF filing in different countries which are USA, CANADA, and EUROPE. In USA, CANADA the drug master file is known as DMF only but in EUROPE it is known as ASMF (active substance master file).^[21]

Sravanti Veera Kota Lakshmi et al., (2021) A Drug Master File (DMF) covers all comprehensive, accurate, and precise information about Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) or Finished Product Dosage Form (FP). It is a confidential document that contains complete, factual, and correct information about the active pharmaceutical ingredient and drug product's chemistry, manufacture, stability, purity, impurity profile, packaging, and the cGMP (Current Good Manufacturing Practices) status of any human drug product. When a DMF is filed, it allows a company to safeguard its intellectual property from its partner while complying with regulatory requirements when its process details are disclosed. There is no legalized or regulatory requirement to file a DMF. A DMF comprises of two parts: (a) the Applicant's Part (Open Part), which contains all the information to assess the quality that the license-holder requires and submit a license or amendment application; and (b) the Restricted Part (Closed Part), which contains confidential information about the manufacturing procedure which is only disclosed to the authorities. A DMF can be used by a holder who establishes the file or by one or more parties to support their files or applications. The present study is to brief an overview of DMF filing in different countries, which are the USA, Europe, and India. It also

gives information on regulatory requirements of Drug Master Files by Food and Drug Administration (USA), European Medicines Agency (Europe), and Central Drug and Standard Control Organization (India) and their comparison.^[22]

Indu Gurram et al., (2017) Purpose: The submission of a DMF is not required by law or FDA regulation, it is submitted solely at the discretion of the DMF holder. The DMF contains factual and complete information on a drug product's chemistry, manufacture, stability, purity, impurity profile, packaging, and the cGMP status of any human drug product. The present work gives the Detailed idea on how to file Drug Master File in US, EUROPE, CANADA, AUSTRALIA. Approach: A Drug Master File is a submission of information to the FDA to permit the FDA to review this information in support of a third party's submission without revealing the information to the third party. In US, DMF filing was done through NDA for drugs, ANDA for generics and BLA for Biologics. In Europe, DMF filing was done through MAA via centralized procedure for eligible products and for other products via decentralized procedure was used. In CANADA, DMF filing was done through NDS for both drugs and biologic products, where as in AUSTRALIA different application processes and regulatory requirements apply depending on the type of therapeutic goods that is applied. Findings: This gives you clear vision on how to file Drug master file in US, EUROPE, CANADA and AUSTRALIA. This paper also gives you the comparison of DMF fling procedure in the above-mentioned countries so that reader can have clear idea on how to file DMF and different concerns on DMF among the above counties. Conclusion: The DMF contains factual and complete information on a drug product's chemistry, manufacture, stability, purity, impurity profile, Packaging and the cGMP status of any Drug product for humans. The content and the format for Drug Master File is used to obtain marketing Authorization. The main objective of the DMF is to support regulatory requirements of a medicinal product to prove its quality, safety and efficacy. This helps to obtain a marketing authorization grant. Now from 2016 onwards most of the regulated countries will use eCTD or their electronic format for their DMF submission.^[23]

M. Vaseem Akram et al., (2014) The pharmaceutical industry is one of the most regulated industries; no drug would be marketed without the teams of medical researchers and other specialists who worked to make sure it receives regulatory authority's approval. A regulatory authority is an agency of the government that is responsible for protecting public health in safety aspects. A Drug Master File is a confidential document used to provide detailed

information about facilities, processes or articles used in the manufacturing process, packaging and storing of one or more human drug. A drug master file comprises two parts: the Applicant's Part, which contains all the information that the license-holder needs to assess the quality and submit a license or amendment application; and the Restricted Part, which contains confidential information about the manufacturing procedure that only needs to be disclosed to the authorities. This review article provides information on regulatory requirements of Drug Master Files by Food and Drug Administration (USA), European Medicines Agency (Europe) and Health Canada (Canada) and their comparison.^[24]

B. Keerthi et al., (2020) Pharmaceutical manufactures need to prepare a document and submitted solely at its discretion to the appropriate regulatory authority in the intended drug market. The file is known as the DMF in US and EDMF in EU the work into compares the drug master files between USFDA and EU for drug registration process and also vision to gain the research about Para IV filling in US and IPR in EU which is useful for the knowledge on drug patents. The literature work, the comparison parameters, difference in filing process of DMF and EDMF requirements has been studied and explained in detailed in this work, which gives the clear over view of the role of filing the DMF and EDMF. It also gives an outline work of PARA IV filings and IPR Studies.^[25]

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

Pharmaceutical manufactures need to prepare a document and submitted solely at its discretion to the appropriate regulatory authority in the intended drug market. The file is known as the DMF in US and EDMF in EU the work into compares the drug master files between USFDA and EU for drug registration process and also vision to gain the research about Para IV filling in US and IPR in EU which is useful for the knowledge on drug patents. The literature work, the comparison parameters, difference in filing process of DMF and EDMF requirements has been studied and explained in detailed in this work, which gives the clear over view of the role of filing the DMF and EDMF. It also gives an outline work of PARA IV filings and IPR Studies.

DISCUSSION

DMF Filing Procedure

According to 21 CFR 314.420, Applications for FDA Approval to Market a New Drug, the FDA discusses requirements for submitting a DMF. The DMF should be in the English language. Whenever a submission contains information in another language, it should be

accompanied by a certified English translation.

Aside from the User Fee Form, no other forms should be filled out or submitted along with a DMF submission. Letters of Authorization (LOAs) submitted with initial DMF submission must contain the DMF number. Each page of each copy of the DMF should be dated and consecutively numbered and any updates should include an updated table of contents.

DMF submissions should include

- Transmittal letter
- Administrative information, and
- The specific information involved in the DMF.

The transmittal letter for an original DMF should cover the following

- Identification of submission: Original, the type of DMF, and it's subject;
- Identification of the applications, if known, that the DMF is intended to support, including the name and address of each sponsor, applicant, or holder, and all relevant document numbers;
- Signature of the holder authorized representative or agent;
- Name and title of the signer.

The administrative information required is as follows.

The names and addresses of the following must be provided.

- DMF holder;
- Corporate headquarters;
- Manufacturing/processing facility;
- Agent(s), if any;
- Contact for FDA correspondence; this is the contact person and a telephone number; fax number and email address should be provided;
- The specific responsibilities of each person;
- A statement of commitment;
- A signed statement by the holder certifying that the DMF is current and that the DMF holder will comply with the statements made in it.^[2]

To ensure DMFs are current, the FDA sends "Overdue Notification Letters" to companies that do not submit a report every three years. The holder has 90 days in which to respond and submit its annual report. If they fail to respond, their DMF may be closed.^[7]

Letter of Authorization DMF

Holders must submit a letter of authorization to FDA in support of an application permitting the FDA to reference the DMF.

It should include

- Date
- Name of DMF holder
- DMF number
- Name of person authorized for incorporating information in the DMF
- Specific products covered by DMF
- Section number & page number to be referenced
- Statement of commitment that the DMF is current & that the DMF holder will comply with the statements made in it.
- Signature of the Authorized person.

DMF Filing, Assessment & Review

- DMF holder should send two copies to FDA
- Then DMF is entered into the database system, a number is assigned, and an acknowledgement letter is sent to the holder.
- A DMF won't be reviewed unless it is referenced with an application, so the applicant should include a copy of their letter of authorization in their application as it is the only way to trigger the FDA's review of the DMF.
- If the reviewer finds any deficiency the reviewer will issue a letter to the holder stating the deficiencies but will not describe the nature of deficiencies.

Obligations of Holder

- Any change or addition in DMF or authorization related to specific customers should be submitted in duplicate copy and with reference to the previous submission.
- The reference should include the date, volume, section and / page number affected.
- A DMF should contain a list of persons authorized to incorporate the information in the DMF by reference (21 CFR 314.420).
- The DMF holder should update the list in the annual update. It should contain the holder's name, DMF number and date of the update.
- If any person's authorization is withdrawn during the previous year, it should be identified under a suitable & different caption.^[9]

Closure of a DMF

To close a DMF, the holder must submit a request to the DMF staff and indicate that the holder has fulfilled all of his or her obligations.

When a DMF holder fails to update the references and changes in the annual update report promptly from previous updates, the agency may close the DMF.

Reactivating a Closed DMF

Upon submitting a reactivation request, the holder is required to submit a complete copy of the DMF, including any revisions since the last submission. Once the request has been entered into DARRTS, the status of the DMF becomes "ACTIVE".

DARRTS: Document archiving reporting and regulatory tracking, it is an archival system of record for all new and subsequent INDs, NDAs, DMFs, BLAs, ANDA's.^[10]

Fig. 1: Mechanism of drug master file.

ASMF Filing Procedure ASMF includes two parts

- 1. Applicant's Part:** The document is open and contains the information that is said to be non-confidential to the applicant. It should contain adequate information so that the applicant can take full responsibility for the evaluation of suitability for the active

substance which is used in the manufacturing of a specified medicinal product. Applicant part still can be considered confidential because it cannot be submitted by anyone to the third parties without the written consent of the EDMF holder.

- 2. Restricted Part:** It is closed, contains all the information which is considered confidential, and all the information such as detailed information about individual steps of manufacturing methods like reaction conditions, temperature, validation data of critical steps, where the EDMF is provided in CTD format, both summaries should be provided in Quality overall summary type. Both applicants and restricted parts should have version no. and the structure of version no. should be unique and follow a logical order.

Contents of the ASMF

The EDMF should contain all the details related to scientific information for market authorizations for medicinal products in the member states of the European Union.

EDMF, linked to human medicinal products should be present in CTD format, and EDMF linked to the veterinary medicinal products should include.

- Name and site of active substance manufacturer
- Nomenclature
- Description
- Outline of the manufacturing route
- A detailed description of the manufacturing method
- Quality control during manufacture
- Development chemistry
- Analytical validation
- Impurities
- Batch analysis
- Stability studies

European DMF Filing Procedure

The active substance manufacturer provides the applicant's part DMF to the applicant which contains both the applicant & restricted part & then it becomes part of the market authorization application which is then submitted to the authorities.

The main objective of the ASMF is to maintain confidentiality & to protect the information about the active substance, while at the same front allowing the applicant to take full

responsibility for the quality, safety & efficacy of the medicinal product. Then National competent authorities assess the complete information which is necessary to check the suitability of active substances in medicinal products.

The EDMF holder should submit to the applicant

- A copy of the latest version of the applicant's part
- A copy of the quality overall summary on the latest version of the applicant's part
- The letter of access, if it is not submitted before for the product.
- EDMF holders need to submit the EDMF to the competent authorities when they submit an MAA (market authorization application) or MAV (market authorization variation).

Updates and Changes to ASMF

The holders of EDMFs of all medicinal products should keep the content of their EDMFs updated in light of actual synthesis or manufacturing procedures.

A change to the EDMF should only be made with the written consent of the applicant and competent authority.

Before making any change in EDMF, EMEA and the applicant should be informed. All the changes should be mentioned in a cover letter.

The cover letter to the EMEA should contain the following info.

- A summary of all the changes carried out since 1st submission of the EDMF
- A comparison between old and new contents of EDMF
- Information regarding, whether the change has been accepted, rejected, or withdrawn by other member states.
- An updated quality overall summary
- The new applicant's part / restricted part with each a new version number.

TAB 2: Comparative Study of DMF's in USA & Europe.

S.no	Requirements	US FDA	EUROPE
1	Regulatory Authority	Food and Drug Administration(FDA)	European Medicine Agency (EMA)
2	Use of DMF in Support of Application	IND, NDA, ANDA	MAA
3	Mandatory	No	No
4	Provide Information	Drug Substance Intermediate, Drug Products, Flavours Etc.	Active Substance
5	Fees for Assessment	ANDA Case Only	No Fee
6	Submission in CTDFormat	Required	Required
7	Forms for DMF Filling	Not Applicable Except Type II DMF, Form FDA3794	Not Applicable
8	Language	English	English
9	Electronic Submission	eCTD	eCTD
10	DMF Number Assigned by Reviewers	yes	No
11	Approved/Disapproved by Regulatory Authority	Not Approved Only Accepted In Support Of Applications	Only Accepted
12	Deficiency Letter	Applicable	Applicable
13	Changes and Approved	Applicable	Applicable
14	Appointment of In Country Care Taker	Applicable	Applicable
15	Letter of Authorization	Applicable	Applicable
16	Closure or Withdrawal	Applicable	Applicable
17	Reactivation	Applicable	Applicable
18	DMF FEES	Only for Type 2, DMF fees will be taken according to GDUFA- \$31,460	New Applications- £5006

PARA IV FILING & 180 DAY'S MARKETTING EXCLUSIVITY FOR FIRST SUCCESSFUL ANDA FILER

(Para Iv Anda Filing = Challenging Weak Patent)

- The Drug Price Competition and Patent Term Restoration Act (Hatch Waxman act) of 1984 streamlined generic drug approval process in US. HWA created an abbreviated process for generic drug approval without conducting costly and duplicative clinical trials. (Under the new legislation, generic entrants need to establish the bio equivalence of its drugs to the original).
- The rules created processes and incentives for both branded and generic companies involving challenges to patents.
- An important section of Hatch-Waxman Act actually encourages generic companies to challenge weak patents.
- If a generic company is the first to file its Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA) with a Paragraph IV certification and prevails in the subsequent lawsuit, that generic

company is granted a period of market exclusivity of 180 days.

- So, it can price its product slightly below the branded version for six months, take market share from the branded product, and maintain its price point before other generics enter the market and erode the price and segment margins.
- The 180-day exclusivity incentive can be significant for a generic company as it would be the only generic version on the market.

PARA – IV Filing & 180 days exclusivity

- By making a Paragraph IV filing, the generic drug maker says the patent is at least one of the following:
 - (1) Invalid
 - (2) Not infringed
 - (3) Unenforceable.

Basic Structure of PARA –IV Filing

INFORMATION ACCOMPANYING AN EDMF

The ASM should give permission to the competent authorities to assess the data in the DMF on behalf of a specified applicant in the form of a „Letter of accesses.

Such a letter should include the following information:

- Name and address of the applicant
- Name of product and, if possible, date of application
- Name and address of the ASM
- Name and address of the importer of the active substance, where applicable
- Name and address of the distributor (agent or broker), where applicable.

A written assurance that is a formal agreement between the ASM and the applicant which

ensures that if there is a significant change in the manufacturing method (likely to alter the quality or safety of the product) or in active substance specification, this information will be communicated to the applicant and to the authorities. It is the responsibility of the applicant to consider any necessary changes in his specification and to inform the competent authorities accordingly. A letter of access must be lodged by the ASM for every application for marketing authorization.

Critical appraisal of documentation of the EDMF

The applicant for the product marketing authorization has the full responsibility for the inclusion in the expert report of the required critical evaluation of the dossier. However, as information in the ASM restricted part of the DMF is not available to the applicant, a critical appraisal should be included in the ASM substance. In particular this section should consider: The manufacturing method and discuss how it will consistently guarantee material of the desired quality;

Batch analysis and whether these show consistency of manufacture;

Demonstration of how the specification and routine tests in the applicant's part are justified in relation to the ASM restricted part.

Use of the European drug master file (EDMF) procedure

The possibility of submitting confidential data to the competent authorities directly from an Active Substance Manufacturer (ASM), who is different from the applicant for the marketing authorization, is provided for in Directives 75/318/EEC as amended and 81/852/EEC as mentioned.

If there is no problem of confidentiality between the ASM and the applicant for marketing authorization or if the ASM and the applicant can come to an agreement safeguarding confidentiality, all of the information on the active substance should be given directly in the application for the marketing authorization.

Submission of EDMF

An EDMF may be submitted if it is referred in a marketing application for a medicinal product. It should be submitted shortly after the submission of the application, so that the reference number given by the competent authority to the application for marketing authorization can be given in the letter of access. The EDMF may be submitted at the same time as the application,

provided an unambiguous reference to the application can be given.

Only ASMs and their authorized representatives (e.g. importers) may submit an EDMF. If an applicant for a marketing authorization wants to rely on alternative suppliers of the active substance, he should refer to this situation in the application.

- One copy of the complete EDMF, comprising the 2 parts (applicant's part and ASM's restricted part) should be sent by the ASM directly to each of the competent authorities concerned.
- A copy of the applicant's part should be supplied in advance by the ASM to the applicant. This applicant's part should be included in the application for marketing authorization.
- Specific quality requirements for certain dosage forms may be included in the application for marketing authorization. Such requirements will not form part of the EDMF. They should be described in a formal contract between the ASM and the applicant and included in the application for marketing authorization.
- If an EDMF has been updated since the previous assessment, the changes should be clearly identified (particularly those in the method of manufacture and in the specifications of the active substance). If a DMF was not presented in accordance with the current guideline on EDMF's (prior to 1992 for human medicinal products and prior to May 1993 for veterinary medicinal products), it should be re-arranged into the 2-part format, and the different parts sent to the authorities.

The specification of the active substance should be identical in the application and in the applicant's part of the EDMF. Any proposal from the applicant to use a different test procedure for the purity tests must be fully validated in relation to the procedure used by the active substance manufacturer, in particular as regards the precision and accuracy of the results of the tests, including the limits of detection for all impurities.

Case Study: USFDA issues warning letters to Ranbaxy Laboratories and an Import Alert for Drugs from two Ranbaxy plants in India citing manufacturing deficiencies.

In September 2008, the USFDA issued warning letters to Indian manufacturer Ranbaxy as it was concerned about deviations from U.S. current Good Manufacturing Practice (cGMP). The Import Alert allows U.S. officials to detain any API and finished drug products manufactured at these facilities (over 30 different generic drugs) at the U.S. border. In addition, until Ranbaxy

resolved the noted deficiencies and came into compliance with U.S. cGMP requirements, the USFDA recommended denial for any NDAs and ANDAs that list the cited Ranbaxy plants.²³

Case Study: Baxter recalls heparin. In January and February 2008, Baxter, a US pharmaceutical firm which manufactures approximately 50% of the US heparin products, voluntarily recalled its heparin due to nearly 350 reported adverse events, including 19 deaths. Upon the initial recall, Baxter and the USFDA revealed that the recalled heparin products contained a contaminated API. The tainted API, imported from Changzhou SPL China, contained a heparin-like contaminant that was structurally similar to heparin and not recognized in the solution until the FDA developed special testing for it. In March 2008, the FDA announced that they had identified the contaminant to be an altered form of an over sulphated chondroitin sulphate which is not a natural byproduct of the heparin manufacturing process.²⁴ In April 2008, the US government held hearings²⁵ and determined the cause to be non-sterile equipment, lack of following proper procedures, and lack of expertise.

To have an API appear in a drug marketed in Europe, API manufacturers need to submit an EDMF (European Drug Master File). API manufacturers also pursue DMFs as the market views them as a sign of quality and they can boost global sales. Figure 327, below shows DMF submissions by Indian and Chinese API manufacturers in recent years and illustrates the recent and stark boom in Indian API manufacture.

CONCLUSION

The DMF contains factual and complete information on a drug product's chemistry, manufacture, stability, purity, impurity profile, Packaging and the cGMP status of any Drug product for humans. The content and the format for Drug Master File is used to obtain marketing Authorization. The main objective of the DMF is to support regulatory requirements of a medicinal product to prove its quality, safety and efficacy. This helps to obtain a marketing authorization grant. Now from 2016 onwards most of the regulated countries will use eCTD or their electronic format for their DMF submission.

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